

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF SUBJECTIVE ATTITUDE SEMANTICS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12578730>

Abstract:

Keywords:

In linguistics, the modality category is studied as the most important feature of sentence semantics. According to V. G. Gak, "modality in linguistics is usually understood as a grammatical-semantic category indicating the attitude of the speaker to the expressed thought or the attitude of the speaker to the content of the sentence." The speaker perceives this objective reality in the form of evaluation and reflects it in his mind, describing his attitude to reality using various semantic categories.

In linguistics, the concept of "valuation" refers to the attitude of the language carrier to things and events in reality, sealed by society. The main method of reflection of the value system is the category of linguistic assessment. The assessment given by a person to the objects of reality, as well as his actions, dreams, goals and aspirations, etc., related to this assessment. through his analysis, an idea is formed about his character, worldview and, in general, the direction of values.

It came into linguistics with a portable meaning, and it means "characteristic of strong emotional imagery". So, expressiveness means expressiveness, impressiveness and is manifested in speech through emotional words, phonetic and grammatical means. Subjective attitude semantics is a crucial area in linguistics that focuses on how speakers express personal perspectives, evaluations, and emotions through language. This field examines the interplay between language and cognition, exploring how subjective attitudes are encoded in linguistic structures. This article aims to outline the theoretical foundations of subjective attitude semantics, highlighting key concepts, frameworks, and contributions from prominent linguists.

1. The Nature of Subjective Attitude Semantics. Subjective attitude semantics involves understanding how language conveys personal viewpoints, sentiments, and evaluations. Unlike objective statements, which describe factual information, subjective expressions reflect the speaker's internal state or perspective. This distinction is essential for understanding the nuances of

communication, as it shapes how messages are interpreted and responded to by listeners.

2. Historical Background. The study of subjective attitudes in language can be traced back to early philosophical inquiries into the nature of meaning and communication. Wilhelm von Humboldt, a pioneer in theoretical linguistics, emphasized that language reflects individual perspectives and subjective experiences. His work laid the groundwork for modern explorations of how language encodes subjectivity.

3. Cognitive Linguistics and Subjectivity. Cognitive linguistics has significantly contributed to our understanding of subjective attitude semantics. This approach posits that linguistic structures are deeply intertwined with cognitive processes. Cognitive linguists argue that subjective attitudes are not merely grammatical constructs but are rooted in human cognition and experience. Key concepts such as mental spaces, conceptual metaphor, and frame semantics provide valuable insights into how subjective meanings are constructed and understood.

4. Semantic Structures of Subjectivity. Subjective attitude semantics involves various linguistic structures that convey personal evaluations and emotions. These structures include:

Modality: Modal verbs and adverbs express the speaker's attitude towards the likelihood, necessity, or desirability of a situation (e.g., "might," "must," "hopefully").

Evidentiality: Linguistic markers indicate the source and certainty of information, reflecting the speaker's stance (e.g., "apparently," "reportedly").

Evaluative language: Words and phrases convey positive or negative judgments (e.g., "wonderful," "terrible").

Expressive elements: Interjections, exclamations, and prosodic features (intonation, stress) signal emotional states and attitudes.

5. The Role of Context in Subjective Attitude Semantics. Context plays a vital role in interpreting subjective attitudes. Pragmatics, the study of language in use, emphasizes that meaning is not solely derived from linguistic forms but also from contextual factors such as speaker intentions, social norms, and situational cues. Understanding subjective attitudes requires considering the broader communicative context, including the relationship between interlocutors and the cultural background of the interaction.

6. Cross-Linguistic Perspectives. Subjective attitude semantics varies across languages and cultures. Cross-linguistic studies reveal diverse ways in which

languages encode subjectivity, reflecting different cognitive and cultural orientations. For example, some languages have rich systems of evidentiality, while others rely more on contextual cues. Examining these differences enhances our understanding of the universal and language-specific aspects of subjective attitudes.

7. Applications and Implications.

Understanding subjective attitude semantics has practical applications in several fields:

Language teaching: Helps learners understand and use evaluative language effectively.

Translation: Ensures accurate conveyance of subjective nuances across languages.

Artificial intelligence: Improves natural language processing systems' ability to detect and interpret subjective content.

Interpersonal communication: Enhances awareness of how subjective attitudes influence interactions and relationships.

The study of subjective attitude semantics provides valuable insights into how language reflects and shapes human cognition and experience. By exploring the theoretical foundations of this field, we gain a deeper understanding of the intricate ways in which subjective meanings are constructed and communicated. Future research in subjective attitude semantics promises to further elucidate the complexities of language and thought, contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of human communication.

References:

1. Rajapova, M., & Sheraliyeva, N. (2022). Teaching english through fairytales. *Scientific Research Results in Pandemic Conditions (COVID-19)*, 1 (06), 186-189. Retrieved from.
2. Rajapova, M., & Sheraliyeva, N. (2022). Teaching english through fairytales. *Scientific Research Results in Pandemic Conditions (COVID19)*, 1 (06), 186-189.
3. Nishonova, S. M., Sheraliyeva, N. A. Q., & Satimova, H. K. (2021). THE IMPORTANCE OF INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(5), 958-965.
4. Rajapova, M., & Sheraliyeva, N. (2020). Teaching english through fairytales. *Результаты научных исследований в условиях пандемии (COVID-19)*, 1(06), 186-189.

5. Ganiyevich, M. T., & Saminovna, M. D. (2023). Factors in The Formation of a Healthy Lifestyle Among University Students. *Journal of Advanced Zoology*, 44(5).
6. Ganievich, M. T. (2023). STUDYING PHRASEOLOGY IN UNIVERSITIES. *Confrencea*, 12(12), 122-127.
7. Mirzaliev, T. G. (2022). The effectiveness of the use of innovative methods in teaching Russian language and literature. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 8.036, 11(12), 296-298.
8. Mirzaliev, T. G. (2023). SCIENTIFIC TEXT AS A SOURCE OF ENRICHMENT OF PROFESSIONAL SPEECH. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(3), 84-88.
9. Tajiyeva, F., & Mirzaliyeva, D. (2020, November). HIGH ALTITUDE DISTRIBUTION OF ENDEMIC SPECIES OF THE GENUS SCUTELLARIA L. IN THE FLORA OF UZBEKISTAN. In *Archive of Conferences* (Vol. 9, No. 1, pp. 57-59).
10. Dilfuza, M. (2023, June). EXPLORING THE BENEFITS OF BILINGUALISM IN EARLY CHILDHOOD. In " CANADA" INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON DEVELOPMENTS IN EDUCATION, SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES (Vol. 9, No. 1).
11. Ganiyevich, M. T., & Saminovna, M. D. (2023). Factors in The Formation of a Healthy Lifestyle Among University Students. *Journal of Advanced Zoology*, 44(5).
12. Saminovna, M. D., & Solijanovna, M. D. (2021). Integrated Approach to Russian Language Lessons. *Academicia Globe*, 2(04), 179-182.
13. Aliyevna, Y. D. (2023). Translational problems of adjectives from English into Uzbek.
14. Aliyevna, Y. D., & Omarovna, S. G. (2023). LEXICAL CONVERSION AND ITS REALIZATION. *Gospodarka i Innowacje*, 36, 346-350.
15. Aliyevna, Y. D. (2023). CATEGORIZATION OF LANGUAGE UNITS. *Gospodarka i Innowacje*, 36, 343-345.
16. Aliyevna, Y. D. (2023). THE ISSUE OF THE SUBJECT AND ITS RELATION TO SYNTACTICS AND SEMANTICS. *Gospodarka i Innowacje*, 36, 214-217.